

efficiency were determined for each combination of parameters.

All the tested parameters showed statistical interrelations. Efficiencies were highest at high static heads, slower speeds of rotation, with three rollers attached and with a clearance of 8 mm. The power required to rotate the pump increased with number of rollers, speed of rotation and static head, and with decreasing clearances.

The tube materials differed greatly in durability and performance. Efficiencies for neoprene tubing were about 30% at a high head, but at low speeds of rotation, its durability was drastically reduced due to bulging and finally bursting of the hose at the pump exit. An unused polyester-reinforced tube proved to have a much longer lifetime, even at low speeds and

high static heads. The number of rollers and the clearance, however, had significant effects on the self-priming abilities of this tubing.

With two rollers attached, a clearance of 9 mm, and a rotation speed of 36 RPM, the pump was self-priming even at a head of 10.53 m, but efficiency was drastically reduced by back-flow. With four rollers, the chemical hose was unable to self-prime. At an efficiency of about 36%, a maximum power of 59.8 W was needed to operate the pump with three rollers attached, a clearance of 8 mm, and 24 RPM to deliver about 11 liters/min to a head of 10.53 m. We predict that a stream flow of about 0.7 m/s can provide the required power of 60 W to drive this pump if attached to an

undershot waterwheel with an efficiency of 20% and a paddle surface area of 1 m²,

The efficiency of the pump decreased under the same experimental conditions to about 10% with an input power requirement of about 50 W. The polyester-reinforced chemical hose survived 1 million cycles of tube compression and self-restitution in a durability test at a static head of 10.53 m. This is equivalent to about 600 h or 25 days of continuous field operation at 10 RPM and three rollers. Ideally, a tube material with the combined flexibility of the neoprene tubing and the durability of the polyester-reinforced hose is needed.

An achieved efficiency of about 30% at high heads, combined with reduced power requirements at low rotation speeds, indicates the potential of the peristaltic pump. □

Front and half-section views of peristaltic pump with 3 sets of rollers.

ENVIRONMENT

Relationships among methane emission from flooded ricefields, solar radiation, straw incorporation, and yield

F. T. Turner and M. F. Jund, Texas A & M University Agricultural Research Center, Rt 7 Box 999, Beaumont, Texas 77713; R. L. Sass and F. M. Fisher, Biology Department, Rice University, P. O. Box 1892, Houston, Texas 77251, USA

Many questions exist about potential physiochemical changes in the atmosphere due to increased methane emissions from rice plants growing in flooded soil. We assessed some of the key factors influencing methane production and emission from typical silty-clay rice soils near Beaumont, Texas. We grew the cultivar Jasmine 85, which matures about 140 d after emergence from Apr plantings, under

conventional drill-seeded culture during 1990. We maintained 10 cm of water from about 30 d after emergence to about 10 d before harvest. We took weekly duplicate 30-min methane samples from 0.4-m² open-bottom chambers with rims that rested below the water surface.

Methane flux determinations showcu significant methane emission of at least 100 mg/m² per d through rice plants, beginning about 10 d after soil flooding.

Methane emission increased with flood duration and peaked at 400-1,000 mg/m² per d near panicle differentiation and heading. It decreased as plants matured and became insignificant upon field draining for harvest.

Average daily methane emission from three 30-d interval rice plantings increased from 275 to 440 mg/m² per d while average daily solar radiation during the 21 d before and after heading increased from 39 to 44 to 49 Einsteins/d, respectively, for the 18 Jun, 18 May, and 13 Apr plantings (see figure). Seasonal average daily mean temperature for the three growing periods was only 26-28°C. Although our previous studies illustrate that temperature (both diel and average daily) has a pronounced effect on methane emission, these data suggest that it is not temperature but solar radiation and the factors associated with it that are responsible for the differences in methane emission over the three growing periods.

Grain yield also increased from 7.4 to 10.0 t/ha as solar radiation increased (see figure), showing a positive relationship between methane emission, rice yield, and solar radiation. These data indicate that the improved world rice yields attributed to modern varieties and cultural practices may actually have increased methane emission from ricefields and contributed to

the reported increases in global atmospheric methane.

We evaluated the effect of organic matter (OM) incorporation on methane emission by incorporating 6 t bahia (*Paspalum*) hay/ha into the top 7 cm of soil 1 wk before planting in half of each of the three planted areas mentioned above. The areas with and without added OM received identical cultural treatments. Even in the areas with added straw, a positive relationship between methane emission, solar radiation, and rice yield occurred (as in figure). Added straw, however, lowered rice yield by 15% for Apr, 8% for May, and 13% for Jun plantings, but increased methane emission by 30, 56, 22%, respectively.

We expected the added straw to supplement the substrate for methanogens (bacteria that produce methane) and to increase methane production and its subsequent emission. We did not expect the decrease in rice yields due to soil-incorporated straw because it appeared to contain enough N such that it did not alter N availability or aboveground biomass. Although we have no data to explain this yield decrease, we hypothesize that excess straw incorporation can create toxic soil conditions that cause the roots of some rice cultivars to “leak” photosynthate, which is then converted to methane and results in

Rice yield and average daily methane emission as influenced by average daily solar radiation during the 21 d before and after heading for the Apr, May, and Jun plantings with and without incorporated straw.

increased methane emission and reduced rice yield.

Despite the rather limited sample of the population, this report shows that seasonal methane emissions can vary from 22 to 48 g/m² because of solar radiation and straw incorporation. □

SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACT

Trend analysis of farmers' share of consumers' rice price in Sri Lanka

M. Wijeratne and T. L. L. Chandrakumara, Agricultural Economics Department, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ruhuna, Mapalana, Sri Lanka

We studied the trends of farmers' share of consumers' prices in the rice production system in two major rice-producing districts—Polonnaruwa and Hambantota—and two main consumption districts—Colombo and Kandy. We collected farmgate and retail market prices just after the harvest (Mar-Apr) of We major rice crop (Aug-Feb) in the

districts from 1981 to 1990. Average prices were calculated for a particular season. Farmers' share of consumers' price was computed from these data.

The results illustrate that the farmers' share as a percentage of the consumers' price declined in all four districts during the reference period (see figure). Farmers in the rice-surplus districts received a slightly higher price because of the competition between organized millers and wholesale traders. Farmers in 1990 received less than 50% of the price paid by consumers. The purchases made through the state-guaranteed price scheme, implemented by the Paddy Marketing Board, was one major reason for this situation. □

Farmers' share of consumers' price of rice, Sri Lanka.